

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Mendeleev's Garden

Question sheet

Print and cut out for preparing the
question deck

Hydrogen

It is the most common element in the universe

TRUE

Hydrogen

The hydrogen molecule is H₃

FALSE, H₂

Nitrogen

It's a poisonous gas

FALSE, but it is suffocating

Nitrogen

It's boiling temperature is -196°C

TRUE

Fluorine

Its name derives from the mineral "fluorite"

TRUE

Fluorine

Elemental fluorine is a red-coloured gas

FALSE, it is yellow

Beryllium

It is very toxic

TRUE, it can cause beryllium disease and is carcinogenic

Beryllium

It is very abundant on Earth

FALSE, in the Earth's crust, approximately 3 parts per million are found

Sodium

When burned, it produces a red flame

FALSE, yellow

Sodium

It is the fourth most abundant element in the Earth's crust

TRUE

Carbon

Its name derives from the name of the "pasta alla carbonara"

FALSE, from coal

Carbon

Carbon-14 is used in historical dating

TRUE, it has a half-life of 5730 years

Neon

Its name means "new"

TRUE

Neon

It is a noble gas that does not combine with other elements

FALSE, some compounds with Fluorine are known

Oxygen

It makes up 65% of our body mass

TRUE, Carbon is just 18% while Hydrogen is 10%

Oxygen

It is a low reactive element

FALSE, it combines with almost all other elements

Aluminium

It is the third most abundant element in the Earth's crust

TRUE

Aluminium

It is a very heavy metal

FALSE, it is used to prepare light alloys

GREEN ELEMENTS

Protactinium

Its name derives from it was confused with Actinium

FALSE, it is called Protactinium because it precedes Actinium in the decay chain of Uranium-235.

Argon

Its name means "lazy"

TRUE

Argon

it is recovered from underground deposits

FALSE, it is obtained from the air, where it is present at 1%

Sulphur

Sulphide compounds have a great scent

FALSE, they smell like rotten eggs

Sulphur

It is part of the elements known since ancient times

TRUE, with carbon, gold, silver, copper, tin, lead, mercury and iron

Chlorine

Its name means "green"

TRUE

Chlorine

Chlorine is easily found pure in nature

FALSE, we often find it as chloride

Silicon

It represents the basis of the computer industry

TRUE

Silicon

we find it in sand and glass

TRUE

Potassium

When burned, it produces a purple flame

TRUE

Potassium

It is a slightly reactive metal

FALSE, it reacts with many elements and compounds such as oxygen and water

Thorium

It is highly radioactive

FALSE, Its half-life of over 14 billion years makes it the "longest-lived" of the radioactive elements

Calcium

It's a metal

TRUE

Titanium

It is a light and resistant metal

TRUE

Iron

It is an element known since ancient times

TRUE

Iron

you can make screws, nails, sheet metal, tools, only if it is very pure

FALSE, if pure it does not have excellent properties; its alloys with other elements work better

Titanium

Titanium oxide is used as a red pigment

FALSE, it's a great white pigment

Praseodymium

If exposed to air it turns red

FALSE, it covers itself with a green oxide patina

GREEN ELEMENTS

Rubidium

in metallic form, it reacts violently with water

TRUE

Rubidium

It is contained in rubies

FALSE, a ruby is aluminium oxide with chromium inclusions

Iodine

Using iodate-salt in foods helps thyroid health

TRUE, a small amount of potassium iodate is added to table salt

Iodine

Italy is a great producer of Iodine

FALSE, production is not significant, the largest producer is Chile

Xenon

as a "noble gas" it does not form other chemical compounds

FALSE, it forms compounds with fluorine

Bromine

It is solid at room temperature

FALSE, Bromine and Mercury are the only elements that are liquid at room temperature

Bromine

It has a pleasant perfumed smell

FALSE, its name means "stench"

Krypton

Its name derives from Superman's planet

FALSE, it means "hidden"

Krypton

It can be recovered from the air, where it is present at about one part per million

TRUE

Caesium

It is a metal that is liquid on summer days

TRUE, it melt at 30°C

Caesium

It is used in atomic clocks

TRUE

Samarium

Its name derives from the region of Samaria

FALSE, the name comes from the Russian engineer Samarskij

Gadolinium

It is in compact discs and data storage devices

TRUE

Gadolinium

It is essential for life

FALSE, no biological roles are known

Xenon

Its name means "foreigner"

TRUE

Samarium

It can be used in nuclear medicine for the treatment of some bone tumours

TRUE

Terbium

it's a very hard metal

FALSE, it can be cut easily with a knife

Terbium

It is commonly found with Erbium and Ytterbium

TRUE

Europium

It is used in special inks in Euro banknotes

TRUE

Europium

It is commonly found in its pure state

FALSE, it is always combined with other elements in minerals

Barium

It is toxic but is used in some medical tests

TRUE

Barium

It is a very light metal

FALSE, its name means "heavy"

Lanthanum

Its oxide La_2O_3 can be used to make lenses in telescopes and glasses

TRUE

Lanthanum

It is used in lighters

TRUE

Polonium

Its name derives from Poland

TRUE

Cerium

It is part of the so-called "rare earths" and is extremely rare

FALSE, despite being a "rare earth" it is the 26th element in the Earth's crust

Praseodymium

Its name means "green twin"

TRUE, it is the twin of Neodymium ("new twin")

Radon

Some scientists suggest they can predict earthquakes and volcanic eruptions by studying radon emissions

TRUE, but the method often fails

Francium

Its name comes from France, where it was discovered

TRUE

Francium

It is the least stable among all natural elements

TRUE, its half-life is about 22 minutes

Radium

Its name derives from the fact that it is used in radio transmissions

FALSE, the name means "ray" in Latin because the "rays" it emits impress the photographic plates

Radium

Its name comes from its radioactivity

FALSE, the name means "ray" in Latin because the "rays" it emits impress the photographic plates

Actinium

its name means "ray"

TRUE, it derives from the Greek aktis and like radium, it impresses photographic plates being radioactive

Holmium

Its name derives from the city of Stockholm

TRUE

Holmium

It is used to produce very intense magnetic fields

TRUE

Polonium

It is very toxic as it is extremely radioactive.

TRUE

GREEN ELEMENTS

Erbium

Its oxide Er_2O_3 is pink in colour and can be used to make sunglasses lenses

TRUE

Thulium

Its name derives from the Tullia plant (Thuia)

FALSE, it derives from Thule, legendary land of the north (perhaps Scandinavia)

Thulium

It is very important commercially

FALSE, now it does not have many applications

Ytterbium

Ytterbium compounds are quite common

FALSE, they are quite rare

Ytterbium

Ytterbium and its compounds are very important

FALSE, there are not many applications

Lutetium

Its name derives from Martin Luther

FALSE, the name derives from Lutetia, the ancient Roman name for Paris

Lutetium

Its isotope Lu-177 finds applications in the treatment of some tumours in nuclear medicine

TRUE

Radon

It is highly toxic and can accumulate in underground rooms of seismic and volcanic areas

TRUE, It can come out of the earth during earthquakes

Rhenium

It is quite widespread in nature

FALSE, the earth's crust contains about 1 mg per ton

Actinium

Due to its radioactivity it has no practical applications

FALSE, several studies are evaluating Actinium-225 in nuclear medicine

Astatine

It is thought to be the rarest element on Earth

TRUE, It is thought that there are less than 28 grams of Astatine on Earth

Astatine

Its name means "unstable"

TRUE

Boron

Sodium perborate is a good bleach agent

TRUE

Magnesium

It is extracted from sea water

TRUE

Magnesium

In photography, it was used to develop photos

FALSE, It was used as a flash

Vanadium

It was initially called "Parachrome" and "Erythronium" but then became "Vanadium"

TRUE

Neodymium

It is commonly found as a metal

FALSE, it is found combined with other elements in minerals

Bismuth

It has great application in electronics

FALSE, it has no significant industrial applications

Phosphorus

Its name means "bringer of light"

TRUE

Phosphorus

It appears as a very hard solid

FALSE, it is a waxy, smelly solid

Boron

It is used in fireworks to make green colours

TRUE

YELLOW ELEMENTS

Nickel

It was already in use
3500 years BC

TRUE

Nickel

It is well distributed
throughout the
Earth

FALSE, 45% of the
resources are in
Australia and New
Caledonia

Copper

It is the best
conductor of
electricity

FALSE, the best
conductor is silver

Vanadium

All Vanadium
compounds are
white

FALSE, they are
coloured in various
colours

Scandium

Its name derives
from the
Scandinavian
peninsula

TRUE

Scandium

It is very
widespread in the
Earth's crust

FALSE, it's quite rare

Manganese

It is very toxic and
harmful to life

FALSE, it is a trace
element essential for
life

Manganese

some of its
compounds are
used to produce
brown colour

TRUE

Copper

mixed with tin it
provides bronze

TRUE

YELLOW ELEMENTS

Niobium

It is often found mixed with Tantalum

TRUE

Molybdenum

added to steel, makes it very hard

TRUE

Molybdenum

It has no biological function

FALSE, it is an essential trace element in plants, bacteria and animals

Selenium

It is found in potatoes but also cereals, fish and eggs

TRUE

Selenium

It was only recently discovered

FALSE, it was discovered in 1817 by Berzelius

Tin

It is a very hard metal

FALSE, it is cut with a knife

Zirconium

Its oxide called zirconia is used to make dental implants

TRUE

Zirconium

It melts at relatively low temperatures

FALSE, it melts at about 1800°C

Niobium

in the past it was called Columbium

TRUE

YELLOW ELEMENTS

Lead

It is the element with the highest density

FALSE, the densest is Osmium which weighs about twice as much as Lead

Lead

It can be changed into Gold

FALSE, transforming Lead into Gold through the mythical "philosopher's stone" was the myth of the alchemists

Bismuth

It is believed to be the last stable element in the periodic table (the ones that follow it are radioactive)

TRUE, but Bismuth also has a very weak, non-hazardous radioactivity

Gold

Gold and copper are the only two metals that are not silvery in colour

TRUE

Gold

It is a rare element and for this reason it was only discovered in 1200 BC

FALSE, it has been known since ancient times because it is often found pure in nuggets or flakes

Mercury

it is also called "quicksilver"

TRUE

Mercury

It is present in modern thermometers for measuring fever

FALSE, it was replaced by Gallium because Mercury is toxic

Thallium

Its salts are very toxic and used as poisons and insecticides

TRUE, but their use has been severely limited due to their dangerousness

Thallium

Its name derives from the city of Tallinn, in Estonia

FALSE, it means "green twig"

YELLOW ELEMENTS

Tungsten

It melts at 100°C

FALSE, it has the highest melting point of all elements (3422°C, boils at 5655°C)

Antimony

its name derives from Stibium which means "stick"

TRUE

Antimony

Its use is only recent

FALSE, it was also used in ancient times to make eye makeup

Tungsten

it is also called Wolfram

TRUE

Neodymium

Praseodymium and Neodymium were initially considered a single element

TRUE

YELLOW ELEMENTS

Iridium

A thin layer rich in Iridium has been identified in the Earth's crust, linked to the extinction of the dinosaurs

TRUE, It is hypothesized that this Iridium was contained in the asteroid that hit the Earth about 65 million years ago

Chromium

It is used in the tanning of leather

TRUE

Chromium

It is used to prepare stainless steels

TRUE

Rhodium

It's quite cheap

FALSE, one gram of Rhodium 99.95% costs over 1000 euros

Rhodium

It is present in the catalytic converters of cars and motorcycles

TRUE

Ruthenium

It is very widespread in the earth's crust

FALSE, it is rare and is found mainly in Russia and America

Ruthenium

it's very expensive

TRUE, one gram of Ruthenium 99.99% costs over 260 euros

Cobalt

Its name means "evil spirit"

TRUE, it was the name of goblins who made cobalt be found instead of silver

Cobalt

Its typical colour is cobalt green

FALSE, it's cobalt blue

ORANGE ELEMENTS

Palladium

It is used in preparing white gold

TRUE, in alloy with gold

Palladium

It has very few applications

FALSE, it is used in telecommunications, jewellery, dentistry, automobiles, surgery, photography, catalysis and more

Dysprosium

It has been known since the year 1000

FALSE, it was identified in the late 1800s but isolated only in the mid 1900s

Dysprosium

It is being studied as a control element in nuclear power plants

TRUE

Cadmium

It is used in Ni-Cd rechargeable batteries

TRUE

Cadmium

It is very toxic

TRUE

Iridium

Its name derives from the many colors of its salts

TRUE, from Iris, goddess of the rainbow

Uranium

It is the heaviest natural element on Earth

TRUE

Uranium

It was identified in the year of the French Revolution

TRUE, in 1789

ORANGE ELEMENTS

Osmium

It is a metal useful for preparing light alloys

FALSE, it has the highest density of all elements: 22.6 kg/litre

Platinum

It was considered a waste material in the search for silver

TRUE, today, however, platinum is worth about 30 times the price of silver

Platinum

Europe produces large quantities of Platinum

FALSE, most of it comes from South Africa

Osmium

Its name means "smell"

TRUE

Lithium

It is a metal

TRUE

Lithium

it is a low reactive element

FALSE, it reacts with many elements and compounds such as oxygen and water

Germanium

It is an element of general little interest

FALSE, it is essential in electronics

Helium

It is very toxic

FALSE, it is not toxic but it is suffocating

Helium

It does not bind to any other element

TRUE

Indium

It is widely available

FALSE, the availability of the next 100 years is at risk

Zinc

Alloyed with copper provides brass

TRUE

Zinc

Galvanizing metals with Zinc causes them to corrode rapidly

FALSE, it protect them

Gallium

It melts at very high temperatures

FALSE, it melts at 30°C

Gallium

It is used in thermometers instead of mercury

TRUE

Germanium

It was not present in Mendeleev's periodic table

TRUE

RED ELEMENTS

Indium

It is a component of liquid crystal displays

TRUE

Arsenic

It is present inside our computers and smartphones

TRUE

Arsenic

It has been and is used as a medicine for some diseases

TRUE, for some forms of leukaemia

Yttrium

It is useful for life

FALSE, its compounds cause disease

Yttrium

It is used to manufacture LED bulbs

TRUE

Strontium

Its name derives from the English town of Strontian

TRUE

Strontium

It is very rare in nature

FALSE, it is very widespread, although not very concentrated

Silver

It is used to make mirrors and precious objects but tends to blacken over time

TRUE, it reacts with sulphides producing silver sulphide which is black

Silver

It is very expensive

FALSE, one gram of 99.9% silver costs around 4 euros

RED ELEMENTS

Tantalum

Its commercial importance is low

FALSE, it is a rather rare element and its minerals (coltan = cobalt and tantalum) are the cause of civil wars in Congo

Tantalum

Its name derives from Tantalus, the mythological king of Lydia (Turkish region)

TRUE

Hafnium

Its name derives from the aphid insects that attack some plants

FALSE, the name derives from Hafnia, that is the city of Copenhagen

Tellurium

Its name means "sea"

FALSE, it means "land"

Tellurium

It is a very rare element

TRUE

Hafnium

It is very difficult to separate Hafnium from Zirconium

TRUE, they have many very similar properties

RED ELEMENTS

Periodic Table

The elements were immediately named and given their current symbols after their discovery

FALSE, the first elements, although called by their current names, were represented by drawings

Periodic Table

Currently, there are 115 elements in the periodic table

FALSE, they are 118

Technetium

It was the first artificial element

TRUE, in 1937 in Palermo. Then it was discovered that, although rare, it also exists in nature

Periodic Table

There are no chemical elements whose name ends with the letter "a"

TRUE

Technetium

It is used in nuclear medicine as a tracer

TRUE

Promethium

It is exclusively artificial

FALSE, it also comes from the decays of Europium and Uranium

Periodic Table

all elements beyond Uranium are prepared in the laboratory by man

TRUE

Periodic Table

It was designed in 1869 by Dmitrij Ivanovich Mendeleev

TRUE

Periodic Table

Mendeleev was the first scientist to work on the ordering of the elements

FALSE, There were several representations and ways of ordering the elements already 50 years before Mendeleev

WHITE ELEMENTS

Promethium

"61" was the last empty hole among the natural elements to be filled in the periodic table

TRUE, It was thought to exist but was only produced in 1963

WHITE